

1 **A low molecular weight pl:pC species activates MAVS.**

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6 We characterized the biochemical functions and transcriptional properties of a low molecular weight
7 polyinosinic:polycytidylic acid (pl:pC) species and contrasted this at the systems level to that of pl:pC of
8 classic size and weight. We demonstrate here that pl:pC of low molecular weight activates the innate
9 immune sensor *MAVS*.

10 Citations

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